

ligands act as tridentate and the coordinating sites are phenolic OH, imine nitrogen and enolic OH.

Acknowledgement

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Characterisation of Some Copper(I) and Silver(I) Complexes Containing Tetraisothiocyanato-*N*-diaminechromate(III)

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DURING our studies on those coordination compounds in which both cation and anion are complex ions, a series of complexes of various metal(II) ions with amines, oximes, and schiff bases

containing the anions, such as nitrosopentacyanoferrate(II) and hexacyanoferrate(II) ions were prepared and characterised¹⁻⁴. The present note records the synthesis and characterisation of eight copper(I) and silver(I) complexes containing the tetraisothiocyanato-*N*-diaminechromate(III) ion. These complexes have been assigned to have planar structures on the basis of their magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by suspending copper(II) sulphate or silver(I) nitrate in distilled water and adding required amount of ligand in methanol or water. The solution was then refluxed for 4 h and then treated with ammonium tetraisothiocyanato-*N*-diaminechromate(III) and refluxed again for 2 h. In case of copper(II), sulphurous acid was added to reduce it to copper(I) before refluxing with the ligand. Finally, the complex under study was crystallised out from the solution using petroleum ether and diethyl ether mixture.

Results and Discussion

The molecular formulae proposed for the various complexes are given in Table 1 and are supported by the analytical and molar conductance data. The coordination of various ligands to the two metal ions has been inferred by the infrared data as follows.

- (i) In all the complexes a sharp band appears around 3300 cm⁻¹ which is due to the presence of ammonia, ethylenediamine, urea and thiourea in the complexes. It is assigned to be the N—H stretch, the negative shift of which is due to the coordination of the above ligands to the metal ions.
- (ii) In addition to this, all the complexes also contain two very sharp bands at 2080 and 810 cm⁻¹ which are characteristic of a N-coordinated thiocyanate ion^{5,6}.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Molar conductance in PhNO ₂ Ω ⁻¹
			M	thiocyanate	Cr	N	
1.	[Cu(Py) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Reddish yellow	11.23 (11.76)	44.5 (43.01)	10.00 (9.63)	28.42 (28.75)	19.89
2.	[Cu(en)[Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Yellow	13.92 (14.37)	50.52 (52.56)	10.5 (11.77)	24.93 (25.35)	20.50
3.	[Cu(urea) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Yellow	13.02 (12.64)	46.92 (46.27)	11.00 (10.36)	27.54 (27.90)	24.65
4.	[Cu(thiou) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Orange	12.51 (12.12)	45.00 (44.32)	10.2 (9.92)	26.21 (26.72)	19.50
5.	[Ag(Py) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Pink	18.92 (18.47)	40.2 (39.74)	9.30 (8.90)	19.85 (19.17)	21.05
6.	[Ag(en)][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Violet	23.00 (22.2)	48.20 (47.80)	11.10 (10.69)	22.94 (23.04)	Insoluble
7.	[Ag(urea)][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Brownish pink	20.10 (19.76)	43.60 (43.52)	10.10 (9.52)	25.12 (25.64)	Insoluble
8.	[Ag(thiou) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Pink	18.97 (19.0)	41.30 (40.16)	9.40 (8.99)	24.95 (24.21)	Insoluble

(iii) The complexes 3 and 7 contain urea which is capable of coordinating through nitrogen or oxygen. In both the complexes a broad band appears at 3320 cm^{-1} (N—H stretching) and its broadening is due to its coupling with the corresponding band of ammonia. The carbonyl stretching frequency is observed at 1660 cm^{-1} and its negative shift corresponds to the coordination of urea through oxygen. The complexes 4 and 8 contain thiourea as ligand and in their spectra two distinct bands appear at 1500 and 730 cm^{-1} assigned to C—N and C—S stretches. The increase in the former and decrease in the later support the coordination of thiourea through sulphur^{7,8}.

As copper(I) and silver(I) ions belong to d^{10} or spin-paired configurations, the magnetic moment values of the complexes are expected to correspond only to chromium(III) ion with three unpaired electrons and thus fall around 3.89 B.M. The electronic spectra also shows bands at 2500, 19.00 and 13.50 kK characteristic of octahedrally coordinated chromium (III), as no d-d bands are possible theoretically for the above metal(I) ions.

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Organophosphonic Acids as Complexones. Part-VI. Reactions of Hydroxyethylidenediphosphonic Acid with Bivalent Metal Ions

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IN continuation to our work on metal derivatives of organophosphonic acids¹, we report here the synthesis and structural studies of metal derivatives of hydroxyethylidenediphosphonic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio. In the present investigation, reactions

with bivalent metals, Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} have been carried out.

Experimental

Phosphorus trichloride and glacial acetic acid (B.D.H.) and bivalent metal acetates (B.D.H., AnalaR) were used as such.

Preparation of ligand: The ligand, HEDP, was prepared as reported earlier¹ and was also obtained as an aqueous solution from M/s Aquapharm (India) as a gift.

Preparation of metal derivatives: Aqueous solution of the acid (1 mol) was added to metal salt solution (1 mol) with constant stirring at room temperature. The precipitation was effected by dropwise addition of acetone. The precipitates were filtered and washed with distilled water containing acetone and then dried at $70\text{--}80^\circ$ till constant weight. The compounds were neither soluble in water nor in any other common organic solvents. These compounds also did not melt when heated even upto 270° . Elemental analyses data, using conventional methods, and colour of the compounds have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL STATE, ELEMENTAL ANALYSES
AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compound	Colour and State	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	P	
MnHEDP.H ₂ O	White solid	19.93 (19.83)	22.28 (22.38)	5.67
Co HEDP.2H ₂ O	Pink solid	19.38 (19.71)	21.06 (20.73)	5.6
Ni HEDP.2H ₂ O	Green solid	19.94 (19.65)	19.91 (20.75)	3.3
Cu HEDP.2H ₂ O	Blue solid	21.29 (20.94)	20.34 (20.42)	2.02
Zn HEDP.2H ₂ O	White solid	20.97 (21.40)	20.10 (20.30)	—
Cd HEDP.2H ₂ O	White solid	31.94 (31.89)	17.39 (17.59)	—

IR spectra (nujol, KBr) were taken on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra were run on an Unicam SP-700 spectrophotometer with a standard reflectance accessory, using MgO as the reference. Magnetic measurements were made on Gouy balance.

Thermal analysis of the compounds were done in the atmosphere of air at National Chemical Laboratory, Pune. The specimens were heated at the rate of 10° min^{-1} in $20\text{--}1000^\circ$ range, and heated alumina was used as the standard.

Results and Discussion

Different bands of the free ligand and its complexes in their infrared spectra have been given in Table 2. Phosphoryl frequency ($1170\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the free ligand is lowered on coordination of the phosphoryl oxygen to the metal atoms of either the same or other molecules². δ_{OOR} mode (1035 cm^{-1}) of the free ligand HEDP is displaced to higher